

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN RESISTIVE INDEX VALUE OF RENAL ARTERIES AND ALBUMIN URINATED IN BOTH DIABETIC AND NON-DIABETIC PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Diabetic nephropathy is a serious complication of type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes. It's also called diabetic kidney disease. In the United States, about 1 in 3 people living with diabetes have diabetic nephropathy. Diabetic nephropathy affects the kidneys' ability to do their usual work of removing waste products and extra fluid from your body.

Objective: To determine association between resistive index value of renal arteries and albumin urinated in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients.

Methodology: A cross sectional analytical study was conducted in 9 months at **National Ultrasound Center**, Abbottabad. 100 patients were selected with convenient sampling technique, Age of 18 to 80 years, both genders, diagnosed albuminuria in urine with both diabetic and non-diabetic patients were included in this study. Patients of renal artery stenosis and extra renal mass were excluded.

Results: Out of 100 patients 58 (58%) were males and 42 (42%) were females who visited the ultrasound department due to complaints of albuminuria in urine. Out of 100 patients 70 (70%) were with the history of type II diabetes mellitus and 10 (10%) were with the history of type I diabetes and 20 (20%) were normal. Males were most likely to develop type II diabetes mellitus than females. The Mean value for Albumin was 60.0625 was in DM Patients and was 17.5950 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was 9.09492 in DM Patients and was 6.32925 in non-Diabetic Patients.. The Mean value for Resistive index was .7464 in DM patients and was .5440 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was .02329 in DM Patients and was .06754 in non-Diabetic Patients. The Mean value for S/D ratio was 1.9999 in

DM patients and was 1.8960 in non-Diabetic Patients and value for Std. Deviation was .05549 in DM patients and was .09689 in non-Diabetic Patients. **Conclusion:** Results of this study demonstrate that resistive index was significantly higher among diabetic patients. . Based on these findings resistive index can be used among diabetic patients to rule out diabetic nephropathy. Being a noninvasive marker and ease of measurement by Doppler makes it an ideal diagnostic marker. **Acknowledgment:** The publication charges for this article are fully/ partially borne from the Khyber Medical University Publication Fund (DIR/ORIC/Ref/26/00145).

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is now one of the most common non communicable disease globally. Diabetes is known as group of heterogeneous disorders with common element of hyperglycemia and glucose intolerance due to insulin deficiency, impaired effectiveness of insulin or both. Diabetic nephropathy is the most frequent micro vascular complication in diabetic patients that occur in ~30% of diabetic patients.¹The chronic metabolic disorder diabetes mellitus is a fast-growing global problem with huge social, health, and economic consequences. It is estimated that in 2010 there were globally 285 million people suffering from this disease. This number is estimated to increase to 430 million in the absence of better control or cure.²⁻⁵An ageing population and obesity are two main reasons for the increase. Furthermore it has been shown that almost 50% of the putative diabetics are not diagnosed until 10 years after onset of the disease, hence the real prevalence of global diabetes must be astronomically high. With the advent of industrialization worldwide and the staggering rise in obesity, diabetes has manifested as a global epidemic.⁶ Although it is very difficult to reach an accurate measure of prevalence for two main reasons: the standard and methods of data collection varying widely in different parts of the world; recent surveys predict an increase in the prevalence of diabetes in adults from 4% in 1995 to 6.4% by the year 2025.⁷ Furthermore, it is estimated to change rapidly with a 42% increase from 51 to 72 million in the developed countries and a 170% increase from the 84 to 228 million in the developing world. Worldwide the number of adults suffering from diabetes will

rise from 194 million in 2003 to nearly 380 million in 2025. The countries most affected by this epidemic in the year 2025 will be India, China and the USA.⁸

Diabetic nephropathy accounts for 25 to 30% of the patients with end-stage renal disease who require dialysis and it has been estimated that 30 to 40% of patients with insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) will eventually develop end stage renal disease.⁹ A number of factors may interplay in the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy, including metabolic, hemodynamic and, as yet poorly defined genetic and/or environmental determinants.¹⁰The National Institutes of Health-National Institute for Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases Bladder Research Progress Review Group's August 2002 report noted that "because diabetes significantly alters the urinary tract, a large portion of people who have this disease will develop costly and debilitating urologic complications."¹¹Unfortunately, the mechanisms involved are poorly understood. The paucity of knowledge has been a barrier to developing the best methods of prevention and treatment of urologic complications." The chronic hyperglycemia of DM is associated with long term damage, dysfunction, and failure of multiple organ systems, including the genitourinary system.¹²⁻¹⁵ Genitourinary complications are common among diabetic patients. Of individuals diagnosed with DM, 80% have lower urinary tract complications, 50% develop nephropathy, and 35% to 75% develop sexual dysfunction. In this article the urologic complications of DM are reviewed. Chirinos JA 2016 Albuminuria is not

present at the onset of Type 1 diabetes. Shortly after the onset of Type I diabetes, the urinary albumin excretion rate (UalbV) is normal or sub-normal. However, in the 35% of patients who later develop persistent proteinuria, UalbV increases in an exponential way at about 20% per year.¹⁶ The rate of increase varies between patients and the intra individual variations of UalbV are quite large. When UalbV is persistently more than 30 mg/24 h, it is clearly abnormal and we speak of incipient nephropathy. After a further 5-10 years, UalbV has increased to more than 300 mg/24 h, which is the macroalbuminuric range at which Albustix becomes positive. Thus, Albustix positive proteinuria is a late event in a long-lasting process which starts shortly after the onset of diabetes.¹⁷

Microalbuminuria (excretion of albumin 30-300mg/ day) is considered to be risk factor for development of macroalbuminuria and leading to overt nephropathy in later stages of disease. Hypertension is an aggravating factor in diabetic nephropathy.¹⁸ It has been shown that treatment of hypertension by angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors delays kidney damage in a large number of patients. Renal arterial resistance index of 80 or higher predicts a poor outcome of treatment and also predicts worsening renal function or death in patients with renal diseases.⁵ In the general (non-diabetic) population, hypertension is the major risk factor for microalbuminuria, and the prevalence of microalbuminuria in essential hypertension is around 25%.¹⁹ Individuals with essential hypertension who develop microalbuminuria have a higher incidence of biochemical disturbances, implying that hypertension per se may not be the cause of microalbuminuria, but, rather, these additional derangements.²⁰ Microalbuminuria is strongly associated with vascular disease in hypertensive patients, suggesting that it is a marker of vascular and/or endothelial damage in this condition. The insulin resistance syndrome describes a clustering of disorders the underlying pathology of which is thought to be related to insulin resistance and/or endothelial dysfunction.²¹ Microalbuminuria is associated with several of

the disturbances found in the insulin resistance syndrome, including endothelial dysfunction and obesity, in addition to type 2 diabetes. Proinflammatory cytokines produced by visceral adipocytes have recently emerged as important mediators of the increased cardiovascular risk associated with the insulin resistance syndrome. These adipokines represent a possible link from insulin resistance and obesity to microalbuminuria in the non-diabetic population.²²

Microalbuminuria can be detected in patients undergoing major surgery, particularly when complicated by sepsis²³, and is associated with other inflammatory states, including rheumatoid arthritis and inflammatory bowel disease.²⁴ Microalbuminuria can also be detected in a significant proportion of the normal non-diabetic, normotensive population (6.6% in one study), where it also associates with cardiovascular disease. Male sex and hormone replacement therapy in women²⁵ seem to increase susceptibility to microalbuminuria, and although the basis for this is not clear, the fact that men have a higher incidence of vascular disease in general implies a common etiology. Hypertension is approximately twice as frequent in individuals with diabetes as in those without, and hypertensive individuals are predisposed to the development of diabetes.²⁶ Hypertension is certainly a major determinant of microangiopathy in diabetes, but the relationship between hypertension and microalbuminuria in diabetes is complex. Hypertension and microalbuminuria often coexist in diabetic patients, and reducing blood pressure reduces microalbuminuria in type 1 diabetes.²⁷ However, it is unclear whether hypertension contributes to the development of microalbuminuria in diabetes. At least in type 1 diabetes, hypertension and microalbuminuria appear to develop together: in longitudinal studies there is no evidence that hypertension develops before microalbuminuria.²⁸ This is more difficult to demonstrate in type 2 diabetes, perhaps because of the heterogeneity of the disease.²⁹

According to the annual report of the Japan Dialysis Treatment Society in 2006, the most

frequent cause of end-stage renal disease is diabetes. Although diabetic nephropathy has been considered to be a microvascular complication, histopathological examination of renal biopsies showed not only typical diffuse or nodular lesions, but also arteriosclerotic glomerulosclerosis.³⁰ RI in diabetic patients with renal dysfunction (chronic renal failure) was significantly increased ultrasonography with color Doppler has enabled noninvasive evaluation of renal perfusion changes by interrogating intra renal arteries.³¹ Among Doppler Ultrasound parameters RI value is considered the most useful and frequently used. It quantifies the changes in renal blood flow that may occur with renal disease. The renal resistive index (RRI) values obtained by analyzing the arterial waveform area non-invasive and reproducible measure to investigate renal blood flow dynamics.³² It is calculated by using the following equation: $(\text{peak systolic velocity} - \text{end diastolic velocity}) / \text{peak systolic velocity}$ RRI assesses renal arterial resistance by the flow velocity variability generated by the pulsatile arterial perfusion. Adult normal RRI values are 0.47 to 0.70 with a difference between two kidneys of 5-8% compared to the patients with non-diabetic chronic renal failure.³³

Duplex Doppler ultrasonography was used to assess intrarenal hemodynamics. The resistive index (RI) calculated from blood flow velocities in vessels reflects renovascular resistance and is known to increase in various disorders. Moreover, vasoactive agents, such as angiotensin II or ACE inhibitors³⁴, are known to affect RI. Regarding mechanisms by which RI of intrarenal arterioles increase, we previously reported that arterio-arteriosclerosis rather than interstitial fibrosis could play an important role. In addition, we reported that there was a direct relationship between RI and arteriosclerosis in damaged kidneys, and RI at renal biopsy may be useful as one of the prognostic markers for renal outcome. Hemodynamic changes, including intraglomerular hypertension, raised renal vascular resistance, and ischemic nephropathy are responsible for the development of various stages of diabetic nephropathy. Resistivity index (RI) of

renal arteries was found to correlate significantly with effective renal plasma flow, renal vascular resistance, and the filtration fraction in patients with chronic renal failure.³⁵ In patients with renal dysfunction secondary to type 2 diabetes mellitus, RI was significantly increased compared with patients with non-diabetic renal disease. RI was found to be a noninvasive diagnostic procedure, which strongly predicted the outcome of renal function in type 2 diabetic patients, even when glomerular filtration rate patterns were still within normal limits. RI was significantly higher in patients with type 2 diabetes with albuminuria than in patients without albuminuria.³⁶

The aim of this study is correlation between intrarenal Renal Arteries Resistive index with Urine albumin excretion, eGFR, serum creatinine and serum cholesterol in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients. Diabetes mellitus is one of the systemic diseases affecting the kidneys. The diagnosis of diabetic nephropathy is paramount for the survivability of the diabetic patients because of the strong association with the risk of developing cardiovascular disease. Duplex Doppler ultrasonography is used to assess intrarenal hemodynamics. The resistive index (RI) calculated from blood flow velocities in vessels reflects renovascular resistance and is known to increase in various disorders. With the rise in the prevalence of diabetes worldwide there is expected rise in diabetic nephropathy. So, a highly accurate non-invasive and specific diagnostic tool for the detection of subtle renal changes that reflects the presence of diabetic nephropathy is highly desired.

Hypothesis

There is association between resistive index values of renal arteries.

Alternate hypothesis

There is no association between resistive index values of renal arteries.

RESULTS

Out of 100 patients 58 were males and 42 were females who visited the ultrasound department due to complaints of albuminuria in urine. Out

of 100 patients 8 were at stage 1, 26 were at stage 2, 32 were at stage 3, 27 were at stage 4, 7 were at stage 5 and males were dominant in in getting in diabetes. Out of 100 patients 70 were with the history of type II diabetes mellitus and 10 were with the history of type II diabetes and 20 were normal. Males were most likely to develop type II diabetes mellitus than females. The Mean value for Albumin was 60.0625 was in DM Patients and was 17.5950 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was 9.09492 in DM

Patients and was 6.32925 in non-Diabetic Patients.. The Mean value for Resistive index was .7464 in DM patients and was .5440 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was .02329 in DM Patients and was .06754 in non-Diabetic Patients. The Mean value for S/D ratio was 1.9999 in DM patients and was 1.8960i n non-Diabetic Patients and value for Std. Deviation was .05549 in DM patients and was .09689 in non-Diabetic Patients.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Gender

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	42	42%
	Male	58	58%
	Total	100	100%

Out of 100 patients 58 were males and 42 were females

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Hypertension

		Frequency	Percent
Hypertension	No	36	36.0
	Yes	64	64.0
	Total	100	100%

Out of 100 patients, 64 patients were with a clinical history of hypertension and 36 were normal

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Diabetes/Non-Diabetes

		Frequency	Percent
	Diabetic	80	80%
	Non-Diabetic	20	20%
	Total	100	100%

Out of 100 patients, 80 patients were with the history of diabetes mellitus and 20 were non diabetic

Table 4: Descriptive statistics for Duration of Diabetes

N	80
Mean	3.26
SD	1.99
Minimum,	1
Maximum	11

Duration of diabetes vary from less than one year to 11 years

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Stage

	Frequency	Percent
Stage-1	8	8.0
Stage-2	26	26.0
Stage-3	32	32.0
Stage-4	27	27.0
Stage-5	7	7.0
Total	100	100%

Out of 100 patients 8 were at stage 1, 26 were at stage 2, 32 were at stage 3, 27 were at stage 4, 7 were at stage 5.

Table 6: Crosstab between Gender and Stage of Diabetes

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Stage	1	Count	6	2	8
		% within Stage	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%
	2	Count	7	19	26
		% within Stage	26.9%	73.1%	100.0%
	3	Count	14	18	32
		% within Stage	43.8%	56.3%	100.0%
	4	Count	12	15	27
		% within Stage	44.4%	55.6%	100.0%
	5	Count	3	4	7
		% within Stage	42.9%	57.1%	100.0%
Total		Count	42	58	100
		% within Stage	42.0%	58.0%	100.0%

Males were dominant in in getting in diabetes than females

Table 7: Frequency Distribution of Type of Diabetes

	Frequency	Percent
Type-I	10	10.0
Type-II	70	70.0
N/A	20	20.0
Total	100	100%

Out of 100 patients 70 were with the history of type II diabetes mellitus and 10 were with the history of type I diabetes and 20 were normal.

Males were most likely to develop type II diabetes mellitus than females.

Table 8: Crosstab between type of diabetes and gender

			Gender		Total
			Female	Male	
Type of Diabetes	Type-I	Count	5	5	10
		% within Type of Diabetes	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	Type-II	Count	25	45	70
		% within Type of Diabetes	35.7%	64.3%	100.0%
	N/A	Count	12	8	20
		% within Type of Diabetes	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	42	58	100

Chi-Square Test=3.325

p-value=0.068

Males were most likely to develop type II diabetes mellitus than females.

Table 9: Group Statistics Resistive Index, Albumin and SD Ratio in Diabetes/Non-Diabetes

	Diabetes/Non-Diabetes	N	Mean	SD	p-value
Resistive Index	DM	80	0.74	0.02	<0.001
	NDM	20	0.54	0.06	
Albumin	DM	80	60.06	9.09	<0.001
	NDM	20	17.59	6.32	
SD Ratio	DM	80	1.99	0.49	0.393
	NDM	20	1.89	0.43	

The Mean value for Albumin was 60.0625 in DM Patients and was 17.5950 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was 9.09492 in DM Patients and was 6.32925 in non-Diabetic Patients. The Mean value for Resistive index was .7464 in DM patients and was .5440 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value

for Std. Deviation was .02329 in DM Patients and was .06754 in non-Diabetic Patients. The Mean value for S/D ratio was 1.9999 in DM patients and was 1.8960 in non-Diabetic Patients and value for Std. Deviation was .05549 in DM patients and was .09689 in non-Diabetic Patients.

Table-10: Diagnostic accuracy of Resistive index in diabetic patients

		Microalbumin level		Total
		<30	>30	
Resistive Index	≤0.70	58(80.56%)	3(37.50%)	61
	>0.70	14(19.44%)	5(62.50%)	19
Total		72	8	80

Parameter	Estimate	Lower - Upper 95% Cis
Sensitivity	80.56%	(69.97, 88.05 ¹)
Specificity	62.5%	(30.57, 86.32 ¹)
Positive Predictive Value	95.08%	(86.51, 98.31 ¹)
Negative Predictive Value	26.32%	(11.81, 48.79 ¹)
Diagnostic Accuracy	78.75%	(68.58, 86.29 ¹)

Sensitivity and specificity of resistive index was 80.56% and 62.5%. Positive predictive value and negative predictive value was 95.08% and 26.32% respectively. Overall diagnostic accuracy of resistive index was 78.75% respectively.

DISCUSSION

The present study was to find out a specific time point in which association of RI variables and albuminuria was evaluated in Doppler ultrasound based study in normal and diabetic patients. In this study, it seems that there is a direct relationship between the various stages of the disease with RI, where its increase has been demonstrated in diabetic nephropathy, especially at an advanced stage, which is consistent with many studies. Ohta (2006) indicated that RI of the renal arteries is linked to the severity of systemic atherosclerosis and is depend on underlying renal disease, and it seems to be more likely to increase in diabetic nephropathy³¹.

In the present study, we showed that renal vascular resistance was higher in patients with macro albuminuria. RI remained significant and was an independent risk factor for the presence of albuminuria. Therefore, RI is a useful marker for the presence of any type of nephropathy found in type 2 diabetes. When we consider the stages of diabetic nephropathy, it is plausible that there is a stage in which albuminuria and GFR do not always correspond to each other. Recent results regarding the pathophysiology of renal disease in type 2 diabetes have challenged the concept that a decline in renal function in patients with diabetes is always accompanied by increased albuminuria. MacIsaac et al have suggested that renal insufficiency, without albuminuria, is common in type 2 diabetes.¹¹ In our study Males were most likely to develop type II diabetes mellitus than females. Anna Nordström also concluded that the higher prevalence of type 2 diabetes in older men than in older women was associated with larger amount of visceral fat in men. In contrast, differences in BMI was not associated with this difference.¹³

In our study the Mean value for Albumin was 60.0625 was in DM Patients and was 17.5950 in

non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was 9.09492 in DM Patients and was 6.32925 in non-Diabetic Patients. The Mean value for Resistive index was .7464 in DM patients and was .5440 in non-Diabetic Patients, and value for Std. Deviation was .02329 in DM Patients and was .06754 in non-Diabetic Patients. Following results shows that Renal RI and significantly related to albuminuria and DM. Which also described by Aya Nakamori, MD et.al. They resulted that single and multiple regression analyses revealed that RI and PI in the two subgroups and in the entire group of patients were correlated with urinary protein level ($p < 0.05$). Comparison of regression lines of each subgroup showed statistically significant differences in two regression intercepts concerning these indices in relation to urinary protein level ($p < 0.001$, RI: 0.71 in non-DM CKD patients versus 0.76 in DM patients, PI: 1.39 in non-DM CKD patients versus 1.60 in DM patients) ($p < 0.001$). Renal RI and PI can reflect damages related to proteinuria and DM.²¹ An Increase in the resistive index may lead to kidney disease. Jörg Radermacher et.al also conducted a study in which 162 patients newly diagnosed with renal disease, the resistance index ($1 - [\text{enddiastolic velocity}/\text{maximum systolic velocity}] * 100$) was measured in segmental arteries of both kidneys. Creatinine clearance was measured at baseline, at 3, 6, and 12 months, and then at yearly intervals thereafter (mean follow-up 3 ± 1.4 years). The combined endpoint was a decrease of creatinine clearance by $\geq 50\%$, end-stage renal disease with replacement therapy, or death. Twenty-five patients (15%) had a renal resistance index value ≥ 80 at baseline. Nineteen (76%) had a decline in renal function; 16 (64%) progressed to dialysis, and 6 (24%) died. In comparison, in patients with renal resistance index values < 80 , 13 (9%) had a decline in renal function, only 7 (5%) became dialysis-dependent, and 2 (1%) died ($P < 0.001$). In a multivariate regression analysis, only proteinuria and resistance index were independent predictors of declining renal function. A renal resistance index value of ≥ 80 reliably identifies patients at risk for progressive renal disease.²²

Results of this study demonstrate that resistive index was significantly higher among diabetic patients. . Based on these findings resistive index can be used among diabetic patients to rule out diabetic nephropathy. Our results also supported by Hamano K *et al* . They conducted a cross sectional study. They resulted that In the patients with diabetes mellitus, mean RI was significantly higher in patients with albuminuria, compared with patients without albuminuria. RI had significant associations with duration of disease ($P < 0.01$), eGFR ($P < 0.01$), and serum creatinine ($P < 0.01$). Many factors are included in development of small vessel abnormalities of kidney as part of vascular damage in type 2 diabetes. The consequence of these abnormalities can be elevation of renal RI, which can be used as indirect marker in diagnosing severity of renal disease in diabetic patients.¹³ Narooeinejad et al. showed that RI can be used to estimate 24-hour urine protein especially in those patients who are not compliant for 24- hour urine collection. Soldo et al. also showed a relationship between RI and serum creatinine. Masulli et al. failed to find a relationship between RI and albominuria which was inconsistent with the results of our study.³⁷

CONCLUSION

Results of this study demonstrate that resistive index was significantly higher among diabetic patients. . Based on these findings resistive index can be used among diabetic patients to rule out diabetic nephropathy. Being a noninvasive marker and ease of measurement by Doppler makes it an ideal diagnostic marker.

1.

3.3: OPERATIONAL DEFINITION(S)

Resistive Index:

The resistive index (Pourcelot index) is a calculated flow parameter in Doppler ultrasound, derived from the maximum, minimum, and mean Doppler frequency shifts during a defined cardiac cycle. Along with the pulsatility index (PI), it is typically used to assess the resistance in a pulsatile vascular system.

$$RI = (PSV - EDV) / PSV$$

Where PSV = peak systolic velocity and EDV = end-diastolic velocity.²³

Albuminuria:

Albumin is a type of protein that is normally found in the blood. It is an important nutrient that helps build muscle, repair tissue, and fight infection. When you have albumin (protein) in your urine, it is called albuminuria.²⁴

Type 2 Diabetes:

Type 2 diabetes, the most common type of diabetes, is a disease that occurs when your blood sugar level is too high. Insulin, a hormone made by the pancreas, helps glucose get into your cells to be used for energy.²⁵

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design: Cross sectional, analytical

Settings: The study was conducted at National Ultrasound Center Abbottabad

Duration: 9 months after the approval of synopsis

Sample Size: Sample size of 80(40 patients in each group) is calculated with 95% confidence interval, 80% power of test and by taking expected mean value of resistive index in patients with and without albuminuria as 0.60 ± 0.04 and 0.69 ± 0.05 . As this sample size is not suitable for conducting a research study. So the we will take sample of 80 (40 in each group)

$$n = \frac{2\sigma^2(Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{\beta})^2}{(\mu_1 - \mu_c)^2}$$

Sample Size For Comparing Two Means

Input Data

Confidence Interval (2-sided)	95%		
Power	80%		
Ratio of sample size (Group 2/Group 1)	1		
	Group 1	Group 2	Difference*
Mean	0.6	0.69	-0.09
Standard deviation	0.04	0.05	
Variance	0.0016	0.0025	
Sample size of Group 1	4		
Sample size of Group 2	4		
Total sample size	8		

*Difference between the means

Z $\alpha/2$ = Confidence Interval=95%

Z β =Power of study=80%

μ_1 =Mean value of Resistive index among normo-albuminuric patients= 0.60 \pm 0.04

μ_2 = Mean value of Resistive index among albuminuric patients =0.69 \pm 0.05

n= Sample size=80 (40 in each group)

Sampling Technique: Non probability, consecutive sampling technique was used.²²

Sample Selection

Inclusion Criteria

Patients of

- Age of 18 to 80 years, both genders, diagnosed albuminuria in urine with both diabetic and non-diabetic patients.

Exclusion Criteria

- Renal artery stenosis.
- Renal and para renal abnormalities

Equipment

Ultrasound: Xario-200 and GE S-8 equipment with both convex probe (3,5Mhz) and linear probe (9, 15 MHz)

4.9: DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

After getting the ethical approval from the hospital ethical committee patients were recruited in the study keeping in mind the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Informed consent was taken from each study participants and all possible benefits and expected risks explained.

The following variables were recorded.

Quantitative variables:

Age, Height, Weight, BMI, Type-II Diabetes, Total Cholesterol.

Qualitative variables

Gender, Diabetes, Hypertension, CKD

4.10: DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data entry and analysis was done by using SPSS version-23. Quantitative variables like (Age, Height, Weight, BMI, Duration of diabetes, Total Cholesterol) are presented with mean \pm SD.

Qualitative variables (Gender, Socioeconomic status, Diabetes, Hypertension) are presented with the help of frequency and percentage. 2x2 table constructed to calculate the Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive predictive value, Negative predictive value and accuracy. T test was applied. P-value ≤ 0.05 is considered significant.

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